

Driven Strategies of Community Justice Administration in Thai Society

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Abstract

The research study aims to formulate strategies to drive community justice administration to be effective and appropriate in accordance with the context of Thai society. The objectives are as follow: Firstly, to study the fundamental information and to analyze the environment of community justice administration in Thai society. Secondly, to compile the concept of creating a strategy to drive community justice administration in Thai society. Thirdly, to synthesize the concept of creating a strategy to drive community justice administration in Thai society. The research study used mix methods which were consisted of quantitative research and qualitative research. The research studied was divided into three steps (1) Designing the quantitative questionnaire by analyzing the community justice environment with 350 people in 19 pilot provinces (2) In-depth interview and focus group with a total of 59 representatives of community justice administrators in PhraNakhon Si Ayuthaya and Phetchaburi provinces. (3) Ethnographic Delphi future research was qualified by 18 experts from the academic person in the university those who work in the field of justice administration including strategic management and the public officers those who are experienced with working in community justice at the provincial and local levels. The results can be divided into three issues (1) Synthesizing SWOT found that, the environment that influences the administration of community justice in Thailand consisted of two important parts which were the strength of the internal environment include having the justice fund, and the external environment which occurred from an opportunity of the government's enforcement of the Justice Fund law. However, threats are lacking a systematic administration (2) The vision of driven strategies of community justice administration in Thai society which is a proactive service for equality and fairness. Moreover, driven strategies consist of four strategic issues as follow: Upgrading the operation of the community justice center, developing a local network, Improving an excellent management system and enforcing the use legal jurisdiction to facilitate justice (3) Strategies for driving community justice administration in Thai society through a case-by-case analysis from experts. There were total of 93 items, divided into one vision, 5 missions, 4 strategic issues, 13 goals, 46 indicators, 24 strategies. Experts have a consensus in the same direction. All of the clauses were consistent between base values and secondary values, and that the interquartile range tendency met the specified criteria.

Introduction

At present, due to the problem of the mainstream justice system in Thai society, which is the main mechanism for establishing the rule of law, is experiencing problems in management from the structure of the justice system that is structurally complex and lacks clarity in unit integration with various government related works. The justice system, especially the criminal justice system, is based on the crime control model. Therefore, it is the mainstream justice system that emphasizes the social control for peace, and the use of the legal process to be controlled by the justice system and extremely monopoly from the state without space for the communities and the civil society to participate and to become a problem in the justice system that focuses on bringing the offenders to punish, thus to neglect in giving the importance to victims. Moreover, lack of processes that promote solutions to problems in the community causes the problem of inequality in accessing to justice. Consequently, the concept of alternative justice, or restorative justice, is an important process in trying to restore victims of crime and correct offenders in the community through community involvement. Participating in informal conflict resolution decision-making process for peaceful community (Williams, 2005).

Over the past years, the Ministry of Justice has been formulating a policy for reforming the justice system by changing the role of the people from being a recipient of justice services to being a participant in making decisions and receiving results from the operation with government agencies to help reduce the mission of personnel in the mainstream justice system. The government emphasizes on ameliorates, rescue and rehabilitation the victims and offenders as much as possible by using the justice reconciliation process in the community. According to the concept of the structural theory and function of Talcott Parson's idea, the society is a system with the different parts (Parsons, 1951). It is related and supports each other. The constant relationship of each part is also a factor that makes the social system balanced. Organizing system about the maintenance and elimination of conflicts means that the system must be able to make the organizations satisfied and regarding to the values of willing "support" the system to survive (Parsons, 1951). However, the management of community justice at the local level still has problems, especially the community justice center has several obstacles in the implementation, such as (1) Personnel lack of knowledge, understanding, and lack of experience in performing community justice tasks, and also the part of the public sector network. They do not understand their roles and responsibilities, the guidelines for driving the Community Justice Center (CCJ) of the government sector. (2) The budget of the CCJ has a limited budget which are the inadequate management caused the budget allocation problems. (3) Materials, equipment and locations are limited causes the problem to allocating the materials and equipment, office supplies, and having some problems about using the electronic. Some do not have the permanent locations to be established, so they need to operate at other government agencies instead. (4) In terms of management, there is a lack of clarity in the operation of the community justice network including with lacking of a plan to drive the mission of the CCJ.

The idea of creating a strategy is an important issue for the Ministry of Justice that should focus on creating a strategy for community justice administration because strategy is the decision making towards the goal directly the use of resources and potential in order to create the opportunities and to prevent the various endangering of the organization (Coulter, 2005), and giving the priority of having a strategic plan that defines the direction and objectives of the organization, then implement the plan as the process for people to develop a strategy to achieve the goals (Abraham, 2006). A suitable strategy should be considered as a strategic plan that is appropriate, or consistent for relating with the agency, and have enough budget to facilitate the system. Furthermore, supporting the agency culture should be considered in order to be successful and changeful (Acker, 2005).

Research problem

The researcher perceived the problem of community justice administration in the issue of the strategic plan clarity for the administration of justice. Therefore, this study was interested in studying to formulate a strategy in order to drive the community justice administration to be effective and appropriate in accordance with the context of Thai society.

Research hypothesis

The idea of adopting alternative justice, or restorative justice, is a significant process in trying to restore victims of crime and accurate offenders in the community by engaging the community in the decision-making process with resolve informal conflicts to bring peace to communities (Williams, 2005).

Consequently, the reconciliation justice system emphasizes on alleviating the mission of the mainstream justice system by focusing on community justice participation. The concept of "Community Justice" has been applied in the Thai justice process to create "Social Justice" to strengthen and empower communities to carry out their own justice activities. It is a community activity by the community itself or with the government in the form of a "partnership" by bringing the core value of the social capital and the community potential to build immunity and safety from crime, fairness and peace of the community (Kityarak, 2007).

Research Scope

1) The area scope of this research studied with justice officers who were working in the community justice operations in 19 provincials in pilot provinces which were consisted of Chiang Mai, KhonKaen, Chachoengsao, SuratThani, Pattani, NakhonPathom, PhraNakhon Si Ayutthaya, Phitsanulok, NakhonRatchasima, UdonThani, Phetchaburi, Lopburi, Chiang Rai, NakhonSawan, Songkhla, Phuket, Chonburi, SakonNakhon and UbonRatchathani.

2) The content scope focused on the concepts and theories related to research, consisting of the concepts on analyzing both internal and external environments in the community justice administration. Moreover, the concept of community justice system dimensions under the relevant laws. Furthermore, the concept

of the strategy justice administration, the fundamentals policy of supervising the justice, and Ethnographic Delphi future research concepts.

3) The scope of population were divided into three groups as follows:

Group 1: 350 representatives of community justice administrators from the Provincial Justice Office in 19 pilot provinces

Group 2: 59 officers from the provincial level community justice administrators and local CCJ's administrators in PhraNakhon Si Ayutthaya and Phetchaburi provinces, those two provinces were the best practice in community justice.

Group 3, 18 experts from a group of experts in the strategy preparation and the community justice which were divided into two expert groups. First, faculty members in Strategic Management and Justice Administration. Second, expertise with experience related to community justice.

Table 1. The scope of population

Group	Population	Number
1	Representatives of community justice administrators	1.1) 350 example group in 19 provincial justice officers in pilot provinces
2	2.1) Justice administrators 2.2) Justice center administrators	2.1) 59 key informants of community justice administrators PhraNakhon Si Ayutthaya and Phetchaburi provinces
3	A group of experts in strategy preparation and community justice	3.1) 18 Faculty members in Strategic Management and Justice Administration and expertise with experience related to community justice

Method

Research methodology

The research on the strategy to drive community justice administration in Thai society is a policy research. The main characteristics were to study of problems occurring in an organization based on interdisciplinary knowledge, including the scope of multidimensional studies of variable factors and the response to organizational needs (Putt & Springer, 1989). This research was a mixed method research which were quantitative research and qualitative research, and can be divided into three steps.

Step 1: The researcher designed a quantitative questionnaire with 350 representatives of community justice administrators, questionnaires were created based on SWOT Analysis, the internal environment using the 7-S McKinsey framework, and the external environment using the SLEPT technique. The index of item objective congruence (IOC) has been used for a questionnaire's validity or concordance between a question and an objective where all of the items have a consistency of 0.5 - 1.0, which was considered consistent with the content and is then tested on a population, and the confidence of the statistical questionnaire was also analyzed by Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient with a confidence value of 0.896.

Step 2: A qualitative research with an in-depth interview and a focus group by using semi-structure questionnaire with 59 representatives of community justice administrators in Ayutthaya and Phetchaburi provinces. These two provinces were the community justice provinces best practice.

Step 3: Using Ethnographic Delphi Future Research techniques (EDFR) with 18 Faculty members in Strategic Management and Justice Administration and expertise with experience related to community justice for confirming the consensus in the driven strategies of community justice administration in Thai Society

Results and Discussion

Results

The results found three main important issues as follow:

(1) Driven strategies of community justice administration in Thai society may be called the “Master Plan” that can be used as a national community justice for the future planning guideline. The Ministry of Justice can use as a model for managing justice at the local level, especially the focus on community justice centers to foster reconciliation in the community. Driven strategies of community justice administration in Thai society was related with the 3rd National Justice Administration Master Plan (2019-2022), and the 20-years Ministry of Justice Strategy (2017-2036). Moreover, the environment that influenced the administration of community justice in Thailand was consisted of two parts. Firstly, the internal environments were considered, and found that many strength points, such as the corroborating between the community justice and the public sector in every provinces include having the justice fund, and weakness were lacking of the public relation from the community justice to the public, and people do prefer to bring the case to the normal justice. Secondly, for the external environment issues found an opportunity of the government's enforcement of the Justice Fund law. However, threat was lacking of a systematic administration

(2) The result obtained the vision of driven strategies of community justice administration in Thai Society which was the community justice was a proactive service for equal and fairness in order to access to the justice. Nevertheless, when studying the internal and external environment, it can be used to formulate a strategic plan for community justice. This was consistent with the concept of (Wheelen & Hunger, 1998) that the strategy-building process has fundamental elements as follow: firstly, environmental analysis, secondly, strategy formulation, thirdly, strategy implementation, and fourthly, evaluation and control

(3) Driven Strategies of Community Justice Administration in Thai Society were analyzed from experts, there are a total of 93 items, which consist of 1 vision, 5 missions, 4 strategic issues, 13 goals, 46 indicators, and 24 strategies. Experts have a consensus in the same direction. All of the items were consistent between the base values and the secondary values, and the tendency that the interquartile range was according to the specified criteria ($Md \geq 3.50$, $Mo - Md \leq 1.00$, $Q.R. \leq 1.50$). Therefore, Driven strategies of community justice administration in Thai society was appropriate, and it has the possibility of taking them into the action. The research study was present the vision, missions and strategies which was discussed at the next part.

Discussion

The result of the research's study, driven strategies of community justice administration in Thai Society, has its vision that ‘the community justice is a proactive service for an equality and fairness in getting to the judicial process. The 5 missions of driven strategies of community justice administration in Thai Society were (1) Participating in surveillance, preventing the crime, and committing the illegal acts in community with the relevant agencies (2) Admitting the appeal problem of injustice, and receiving the whistleblowers misconduct information, as well as help, care, give advice and solve basic problems for the recipient trouble, or those who want basic advice on law and judicial process (3) Reducing the conflicts in the community accordingly the principles of the reconciliation justice and monitoring abide by the agreement between the controversial couple (4) Providing the assistance and the care to the recipient damage, or receiving the impact of crime and coordinating the relevant agencies for performing their duties. (5) Participating in supporting, relieving and rehabilitating the offenders, and those who were acquitted to become the good citizens. Those missions were consistent with the conceptual from the book named “Strategic management: Concept and applications” (Certo & Peter, 1991) which stated a crucial process of defining strategy that was an establishment of an organizational direction by considering an organizational mission which focused on the reason of necessity, and objective of an organization seeking all advantages given from having an organization with its precise direction of administration. Moreover, the result also was consistent with the conceptual from the book named “Crafting Strategy” (Mintzberg, 1987) who proposed the solution guidelines for perspicuity and gap-reduction on two issues of discrepancy: (1) The definition of a strategy must be understandable and viable, (2) The actuality of an implementation of strategy. Practically, an implementation of any strategy may succeed or fail, or adapted according to an ever-changing circumstance. Consequently, a control or follow-up process must be brought in use, so that the strategy was implemented as planned.

In addition, all strategies obtained from the studies found that the strategies were consisted of other research studied as follow:

Strategy 1: Enhancing the operation of the CCJ to support the needs for assistance from public sector. The enhancement of operation needs come from the opinions of the CCJ's officers both local and provincial levels. It

intended that the CCJ was highly capable of providing assistance to all people suffering injustice, and coordinating and transferring lawsuits to all involving agencies directly, so that the CCJ can be the principal agency with its role in providing legal remedies to those suffered from the effects of crime. The issue, particularly, focused on rendering the legal services from the government agencies to all people with the highest efficiency. It showed that any means of accessibility to justice at a local level especially the CCJ must be efficient and effective in delivering justice to the people in accordance with the Theory of Situational Management, or the Contingency (Fiedler, 1967). It was the management theory based on the fact that the decision to choose a solution to a management problem depended on each of the situation. An executive or decision-maker was required to be able to perceive of all differences in an agency: differences among people, rules and regulations, means and ways, stages and processes, and the operational objectives of an organization. Consequently, it is necessary for all government agencies to consider their organizational resources and structural and management flexibility, so that they will able to properly and efficiently adjust their organizations amid the dynamic circumstances around them. According to the public sector studies presented the evidence of the role for the public play in carry organization change (Fernandez & Rainey, 2006). Moreover, public involve in decisions which will affect the ability of all members to continue operations and meet the goals of internal and external stakeholders (Rethemeyer & Hatmaker, 2008). Conclusion, the strategic issue of upgrading the operation of the CCJ must support the demand for assistance people's sector which means a strategic management of the government sector should adjust according to the changing of situation to provide convenience, speed, and modernity to serve the people to achieve the highest satisfaction and to be reliant on the people in order to receive the most efficient service and to get the most benefit.

Strategy 2: Developing networks at the local level to enhance the participation of the public sector with the CCJ. The issue was arisen from various reactions of the CCJ's officers both local and provincial levels. It aimed to be provided with the strategy capable of promoting and supporting the networks of the community justice, and integrating cooperation between all agencies of the government, and private sectors at a local level. The cooperation came in the form of partnership to achieve their missions, and strengthening the network of the community justice with the guidelines for the prevention and protection of all crimes, corruption, and all unlawful activities in a community in order to reduce the problems. It found that, it was correlated with the concept from one of the masterpiece works named "Popular Participation; Social Research; Pearse. Geneva: United Nations Research Institute for Social" (Pearse & Stiefel, 1980) which stated that there were 4 types of participations: (1) Participating in decision-making, (2) Participating in operation, (3) Participating in taking advantage, and (4) Participating in evaluation. Therefore, to have a strong network of a communication justice usually needs participation from the public sector in preventing all kinds of crime and conflicts, and providing remedies to all victims of crime in a community. It could be seen in the Hentic & Bernier work which stated that the rationalization of the state apparatus. In particularly, the decentralization of the government to the civil society have to assist the changing systems of governance, especially at local level, and had a significant impact on their effectiveness (Hentic & Bernier, 1999). Beside, the studied of Zerbinati & Souitaris found that the political science and public management research streams which emphasized Stevenson's classical framework of entrepreneurship can be applied in a European local government context, and found five distinct types of entrepreneurial agents in the public sector: professional politician; spin-off creator; business entrepreneur in politics; career-driven public officer; and politically ambitious public officer (Zerbinati & Souitaris, 2007). These could be said that, local level participants as network in the public sector. Furthermore, strengthen the power of community justice networks and integrate the cooperation between government agencies and local people in the form of partnerships with government agencies can be more concrete results by supporting people to access and participate in services in the alternative justice system. Another thing is the government should require the community justice network for being the guidelines for the prevention, the surveillance, the crime, the corruption, and the various illegal Acts in the community for reducing the crime problems. If there is a community justice strategy that focuses on strengthening the network, it will be beneficial to the justice system by having more effectively and quickly in providing justice. At the same time, improving the ability of community justice network is also required to assist people for approaching the services, and to be professional.

Strategy 3: Developing an excellent management system to strengthen the CCJ. It was originated from the comments given by the CCJ's provincial and local staff. It was aimed to the human development strategy for creating of efficiency in the community justice works. All staffs in the community justice works from the ministry, provincial, and community levels were required to be very efficient in their performances. It should focus on helping the victims according to the concept of "Justice Care" promoted by the Ministry of Justice. In accordance with the research conducted in the titled "Community leadership Development" (Kirk & Shutte, 2004) which involved the development of leadership in a community. The study found that the model with a potential development of leadership in a community possesses were consisted of three factors: (1) Leading change through dialogue, (2) Collective empowerment, and (3) Connective leadership. Consequently, the leader

for the community justice work was required to have a leadership character in order to be efficient in working with the people in a community for reducing crime including the sharing of power, and creating the connection to all involving agencies. Moreover, leadership played the importance role in the excellent management performance. The effect of the cultural empathy, the open mindedness, and the social initiative on performance via transformational leadership has been found in this study. It seemed that both these dimensions of multicultural personality and transformational leadership were needed for excellent managerial performance (Woerkom & Reuver, 2009). Furthermore, it was found that the leadership played the important role in management system. It was mentioned in 7 fundamental of an operationally excellent management system that operation excellent management system promotes full integration among people, processes, systems, and leadership for success (Lutchman, Evans, & al, 2015). Conclusion, the community justice required the leadership to achieve excellence in operating with local residents to reduce crimes. It is also a decentralization and link to other relevant agencies as well.

Strategy 4: Utilizing the legal authority to facilitate justice through the operation of the CCJ. The issue was derived from the comments given by the CCJ's provincial and local staff. It understood that the community justice work at a local level needed time for an adjustment and adaptation, so that the staff and all networks of the community justice were able to aware and perceive of an exercise of legal power. Due to the fact that most of the people were ignorant of the law, then they had no skill of using it as a guideline for their works and activities. As a result, a proper exercise of legal power was very essential for providing any legal advices. The strategy was confirmed that the professional took control and made decisions immediately, so sense of exercises power are necessary for staffs (Maria, Tarja, & al, 2004). However, there were other studies supported the caring power concept was as a way of exercising power through kindness. Nevertheless, the study of Svensson perceived that the supporting and controlling were different interpretations of the actions. It depended on the relationship among the actors involved in different ways. When the actors united in their task, only the supportive aspects were shown, but when the actors cannot unite, the power was revealed (Svensson, 2003). On the other hand, this concept was applied in the exercise of the power in order to require understanding and careful attention in sentencing judge (Scott, 2008). Conclusion, the use of legal powers to facilitate fairness through the operation of the CCJ will be able to operate successfully in accordance with the strategic issues that focus on develop knowledge and understanding in the use of law among personnel in community justice work to create peace in the community.

Conclusion

Driving guidelines for a legal actions.

A significant finding was the law enforcement for the community justice lacked a clear written law. It was urgent that the community justice act must be enacted and properly applied to the current practice of law enforcement. Currently, all operations are based on the ministerial regulations. In view of an administrative consideration, these orders are unclear and unsystematic that there is various overlapping of authorities in the administration of the community justice. In other word, it has not a law indicating clearly of all authorities for the community justice works. Furthermore, a change should be taken place for an adjustment of providing a legal advice in the form of an online service.

Driving guidelines for the policy and planning level.

The guidelines should aim at the regional CCJ to be more efficient in delivering justice and reducing conflicts and crime in the local areas. The guidelines should be operated in each area all over the country by being granted an official approval from the national committee of judicial administration development (NCJAD). The guidelines are then put into practice locally.

Driving guidelines for the operational Level.

The office of provincial justice should perform a performance monitoring, and report it to the provincial committee of the judicial administration development (PCJAD), and inform to the NCJAD to be acknowledged of the operation according to the driving strategic plan of the community justice in Thai Society. Finally, all conclusions were brought to be considered for all possible solutions including the guidelines for the development of the administration of justice. For the issue concerning, the correction for an offender in a community, the concept of "The driving strategy of the administration of the community justice in the Thai society" should be applied to use by integrating the operations of all related agencies. Another concerning issue was the administrating of the justice fund will be successful in a local level depends on the assisting people those who suffered from the crime effects according to "The driving strategy of the administration of the community justice in the Thai society" in order to be appropriate and useful for the protection of the rights of the people.

Recommendations

1. The Ministry of Justice should give significance to the operational continuity of the CCJ. All participating parties should cooperate with each other to the development of a network of communication after a completion of the project so that an exchange of information within the network is built. In addition, there should be an ongoing activity joined by all parties in order to sustain a continuity of all parts of the network.
2. The Ministry of Justice should link cooperation among all agencies inside and outside the organization. Also, the ministry should initiate a mutual understanding in the driving strategy of the community justice administration in Thai society, so that the knowledge received from the study will be further developed until integration among all agencies is created particularly the educational institutions.
3. The Ministry of Justice should focus on a significance of a technological proficiency of all staffs operating the community justice. The online communication service system between the people in a community and the CCJ should be significantly improved, especially a preparation of an IT in a personal mobile phone which will be the benefit for people to enable access to all information involving the community justice, and the legal use whenever they need.

Acknowledgements or Notes

The development of research study is needed on the community. The justice strategies should give the priority to the coronavirus situation in order to be in line with the political, economy and society context. Furthermore, there should be further research and development of strategic issues for driving community justice administration in Thai society to be more effective and more variety. Lastly, either advanced quantitative research, or conducting qualitative research should focus on the trends in the development processes to integrated cooperation with other people's network groups.

References

- Abraham, S.C. (2006). *Strategic planning a practical guide for competitive success*. California Thomson South West.
- Acker, D.A. (2005). *Strategic Market Management*. Seventh Edition, New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Certo, S.C., & Peter, J.P. (1991). *Strategic management: Concept and applications*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Coulter, Mary. (2005). *Strategic management*. New Jersey: Peason Education.
- Fernandez, S., & Rainey, H.G. (2006). *Managing Successful Organizational Change in the Public Sector*. *Public Adm. Rev.* 66(2):168 – 176. DOI: 10.1111/j.1540-6210.2006.00570.x
- Fiedler, F.E. (1981). *Leadership Effectiveness*. *ABS*, 24(5), 619-632. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000276428102400503>
- Hentic, I., Bernier, G. (1999). *Rationalization, decentralization and participation in the public sector management of developing countries*. *Int. Rev. Adm. Sci.* 65(2), 197-209. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F0020852399652005>
- Kirk, P., & Shutte, A.M. (2004). *Community leadership development*. *Community Dev. J.* 39(3), 234-251. DOI:10.1093/cdj/bsh019
- Kityarak, K. (2007). "Community Justice": Opportunity for public participation in the justice process. The Agricultural Cooperative Association of Thailand Printing Company Limited.
- Lutchman, C., Evans, D., Ghanem, W., & Maharaj, R. (2015). *7 fundamental of an operationally excellent management system*. CRC press.
- Maria, S., Tarja, S., Pirkko, R., & Maija, H. (2004). *How delivery ward staff exercise power over women in communication*. *J. Adv. Nurs.* 46(1), 33-41. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2648.2003.02963.x>
- Mintzberg H., (1987). *Crafting Strategy*. *Harvard Business Review.* 65(4), 66–75.
- Parsons, T. (1951). *The Social System*. New York : The Free Press of Glencoe.
- Pearse, A., & Stiefel, M. (1980). *Popular Participation; Social Research; Pearse*. Geneva: United Nations Research Institute for Social.
- Putt, A.D., & Springer, J.F. (1989). *Policy research: concept, methods and application*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.

- Rethemeyer, R.K., Hatmaker, D.M. (2008). Network Management Reconsidered: An Inquiry into Management of Network Structures in Public Sector Service Provision. *J Public Adm Res Theory*, 18(4), 617–646. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jopart/mum027>
- Scott, R. (2008). Risk assessment and sentencing of serious sex offenders. *PsychiatrPsychol Law*, 15(2), 188–201. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13218710802132584>
- Svensson, K. (2003). Social Work in the Criminal Justice System: An Ambiguous Exercise of Caring Power. *J Scand Stud Criminol Crime Prev*, 4(1), 84-100. DOI: 10.1080/14043850310011126
- Wheelen, T.L., & Hunger J.D. (1998). *Strategic management and Business policy: entering 21st Century Global Society*. Massachusetts: Addison-Wesley.
- Williams, B. (2005) *Victims of crime and community justice*. Great Britain: Athenaem Press, Gateshead, Tyne and Wear.
- Woerkom, M.V., & Reuver, R.S.M.D. (2009). Predicting excellent management performance in an intercultural context: a study of the influence of multicultural personality on transformational leadership and performance. *Int. J. Hum. Resour. Manag.*, 20(10), 2013-2029. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585190903175589>
- Zerbinati, S., & Souitaris, V. (2007). Entrepreneurship in the public sector: a framework of analysis in European local governments. Published online <https://doi.org/10.1080/0898562042000310723>

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